

METHODOLOGY OF CREATIVE COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This article gives information about the conditions for the formation of creative competence of future primary school teachers and the ways of developing the creativity of pedagogues.*

Keywords: *competence, primary school teachers, creative competence, competence, creativity.*

In modern conditions, the technological and innovative level of professional activity is increasing more and more, that is, it represents a rationally organized set of specific actions of different levels that ensure obtaining the required result in a real environment. Accordingly, the education system is continuously developing. The Ministry of Education and Science launched a project to modernize pedagogical education conditioned by the changes in general education, the adoption of state educational standards for different levels of education and the adoption of the professional standard of a pedagogue [97]. In the list that implements the competence approach in the field of pedagogy, creative competence takes a rightful place among the competencies that must be formed. In the professional requirements of the pedagogue, an important place is allocated to the performance of labor functions that require the pedagogue's high level of creative preparation and the ability to organize the educational and creative activities of students in general education programs. However, it should be noted. most of the working pedagogues received pedagogical education before the introduction of modern requirements for the development of creativity in educational programs. At the same time, they need to periodically confirm and improve the level of their professional qualifications by passing short-term or medium-term programs of future primary school teachers. In addition, there is a continuous flow of pedagogical personnel from the ranks of specialists who have not received pedagogical education and have work experience in other areas of professional activity. This is allowed by the Law on Education [93]. It is known from experience that in both short and medium-term existing primary education programs, from a personal point of view, but also in connection with professional pedagogical activity, the creativity of future primary school teachers insufficient attention is paid to the formation and improvement of their competences. Thus, the problem of formation and improvement of the creative competence of future elementary school teachers becomes an urgent issue.

Creative competence in the structure of professional qualities and qualities of a teacher is required by the development of innovative processes in the educational system, the differentiation and variability of teaching, and the integration of formal and informal education. This requires the teacher to be able to flexibly respond to the changing needs and requirements for individual and group education, to make independent decisions, to consciously and thoughtfully choose the methods of activity of his teachers from a wide range of emerging pedagogical alternatives. . The effectiveness of the operation and development of the general educational institution depends to a large extent on the level of formation of the creative competence of the pedagogical staff.

The problem of formation and improvement of competences of future elementary school teachers has been studied in various aspects, for example, N.Yu.Karakozova studied the formation of technological competence [36], but the possibility of forming creative competence, which is equally necessary in the implementation of pedagogical technologies, was excluded.

S.A.Salnikova [68] reveals the meaning of the concept of “creative competence” as a key competence that “allows a person to understand the situation and achieve results in the conditions of the increasing dynamism of modern society in personal and professional life”, but here this competence is defined as a future start-up. the question of the possibility of formation in class teachers has not been studied. Today, the Republic of Uzbekistan has an objective need for creative pedagogues capable of implementing innovations in the process of the educational system, therefore, it is necessary to form and improve the creative competence of future primary school teachers. Future primary school In order to form and improve the creative competence of teachers, it is necessary to observe the following pedagogical conditions:

- Systematic construction of the content-procedural subsystem aimed at forming the creative competence of future elementary school teachers in their personal and professional development as a system-forming component;

- Use of pedagogical technologies of creativity development on the basis of organizing the systematic work of creating a cross-activity environment of educational development subjects, which ensures that future primary school teachers enter the process of active independent learning.

- Organization of the training process of future elementary school teachers in accordance with the theoretical model of creativity development in pedagogical activity helps to increase the efficiency of creative competence formation. This model guides the creation of conditions for the free choice of the individual development trajectory of the creative activity of each future elementary school teacher according to his individual capabilities and needs.

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